

ESMO
Earth System Modelling
and Observations

Science and Implementation Plan 2024-2033

July 2025

WCRP
World Climate
Research Programme

WORLD
METEOROLOGICAL
ORGANIZATION

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	2
ESMO Structure and Science	4
Introducing the ESMO Objectives	4
ESMO structure overview	5
ESMO history and antecedents	6
ESMO partners	7
ESMO Objectives in Detail	8
1 - Advancing predictions and projections of the Earth system	8
Topics	9
Integrated experiment and evaluation frameworks	9
New modelling approaches	9
High resolution modelling	10
Methods and Activities	11
Outcomes	12
2 - Improving monitoring, understanding and attribution of climate system changes and impacts	12
Topics	12
Climate observing networks	12
Data assimilation and benchmark reanalysis	13
Uncertainty quantification	14
Methods and Activities	14
Outcomes	15
3 - Advancing and harnessing emerging technologies	16
Topics	16
Emerging technologies for data mining and post-processing	16
Machine learning for emulators and parameterizations	16
Technological advances in the observing system	17
Data formatting, conversion, and sharing	17
Data curation for emerging technologies	17
Artificial intelligence for chatbots and citizen science	18
Methods and Activities	18
Outcomes	19
Pairing Objectives to Working Groups and Partners	19
Cross-Cutting Science Themes	20

Carbon Cycle	20
Extremes	21
Parameterizations and Emulators	21
Data Assimilation and Statistical Modelling	21
Managing Slow and Fast Earth System Components	21
Implementation and Methods of ESMO	22
ESMO Structure	22
ESMO Scientific Steering Group	22
International Project Offices	22
ESMO International Project Office (ESMO IPO)	22
CMIP International Project Office (CMIP IPO)	23
Working Groups	23
Working Group on Coupled Modelling (WGCM)	23
Working Group on Subseasonal to Interdecadal Prediction (WGSIP)	23
Working Group on Numerical Experimentation (WGNE)	23
Working Group on Observations for Researching Climate (WGORC)	23
Projects and Panels	24
Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP)	24
WCRP Infrastructure Panel (WIP)	24
Observations for Model Intercomparisons Projects (Obs4MIPs)	24
Decadal Climate Prediction Project (DCPP)	25
Task teams	25
Km-scale Modeling ESMO-Digital Earths Task Team	25
ESMO Modes of Work	25
Meetings	25
Community Papers	25
Schools and Capacity Building	26
Strengthening ESMO's engagement with Global South	26
Web Presence and Open Access	26
List of Abbreviations	27
Links to Relevant Glossaries	28
References	29

ESMO Structure and Science

ESMO coordinates, advances, and facilitates all modelling, data assimilation and observational activities within WCRP, working jointly with other WCRP projects and providing strategic connections to related external programs. Its scope spans all Earth system components, disciplines, and scales. The modelling and observational activities under ESMO are central to the provision of science-based climate information to support adaptation planning and decision-making, local and regional climate impact assessments, and national and international mitigation and adaptation policies. Such information advises a wide range of stakeholders about how and why the climate is changing and what that will mean for societies, economies, livelihoods, and ecosystems. Understanding, adapting to, and mitigating climate change requires taking a holistic perspective on our Earth system. The strong interplays between carbon, energy and water cycles are well-known examples of climate research's interconnectivity. Correspondingly, the monitoring, modelling, and analysis of climate components is eased by consistent and coordinated effort.

Introducing the ESMO Objectives

Figure 1: ESMO objectives.

The ESMO Science Plan is based on three scientific objectives that will underpin and integrate the next decade of climate science modelling, data assimilation and observational activities (Figure 1). The objectives are informed by the most pressing shortcomings in our ability of monitoring, predicting, and projecting the climate system from days to centuries and from local to global spatial scales with an aim to advance the core capabilities of the programme. The objectives are:

- (1) **Advancing predictions and projections of the Earth system** on time scales from weeks to centuries and furthering model-observation integrated frameworks.
- (2) **Improving monitoring, understanding, and attribution of climate changes and impacts** with robust uncertainty quantification through the combined use of models and observations.

(3) Advancing and harnessing emerging technologies in modelling and observations.

Each of the above objectives benefits from an internationally coordinated, integrated, and consistent framework combining global Earth system observations, data assimilation and modelling. Through the above objectives, ESMO will contribute to our understanding, predictive skills, and improved projections across all components of the climate system.

Many individual aspects of the three objectives are already being addressed in the WCRP Core Projects (CPs), Lighthouse Activities (LHAs) and the WCRP Academy. For each objective, ESMO provides coordination amongst these groups to capture specific priority topics and activities found by any group to be the most pressing needs of the community and within the capabilities and mandate of ESMO. These activities will foster strong collaborations across WCRP, obtaining rapid results and benefits and addressing the cross-cutting science questions highlighted below.

ESMO structure overview

All activities under ESMO are overseen by the ESMO Scientific Steering Group (SSG) which has the overall responsibility for planning and guiding the work of the Core Project (Figure 2). The ESMO International Project Office supports the SSG and the wider ESMO community in their work and is the main point of contact for ESMO. ESMO Working Groups (WGs) coordinate science activities within broad categories to facilitate modelling and observational activities that address ESMO research objectives. WGs are long-standing organisational elements with WG co-chairs and memberships appointed by the ESMO SSG.

Similarly, ESMO Projects and Panels (PnPs) are focused science teams formed within or alongside the Working Groups to address specific needs of the community. Their scope is more limited, and their deliverables more specific, than those of a WG. Examples are the Climate Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP), the WCRP Infrastructure Panel (WIP), Obs4MIPs and the Decadal Climate Prediction Project (DCPP). These bodies are long-standing organisational elements with co-chairs and memberships to be appointed by the ESMO SSG and may involve their own project offices and other resources. ESMO Task Teams (TTs) are shorter-term organisational elements of ESMO that target specific, time-limited scientific goals and outcomes. Their lifetime is connected to envisioned deliverables that are set when the task teams are formed. Task Teams are *ad hoc* organisational elements with co-chairs and memberships convened or appointed by the ESMO SSG, an ESMO WG or an ESMO panel. The ESMO IPO coordinates proposals for formation of TTs and PnPs, and the ESMO SSG reviews the proposals.

Details about the current structure of ESMO, including a brief description of the different Working Groups, Projects/Panels, and Task teams can be found further in the science plan.

Figure 2: ESOM organisational structure.

ESMO history and antecedents

At the initiative of the JSC and following the [WCRP Strategic Plan 2019–2028](#), an ad hoc committee was formed from the former advisory councils, the WCRP Modeling Advisory Council (WMAC) and the WCRP Data Advisory Council (WDAC), to discuss observational and modelling activities. The committee began to formulate ideas and plans for a new core project (ESMO) coordinating and advancing these activities across WCRP in 2020. Exchange within the committee and with the wider science community provided input as to the direction and mandate for ESOM. The outcomes of the discussions were that while modelling and observational groups within the WCRP Core Projects were strong, siloing of ideas and techniques to a particular class of observations or models may be limiting progress, especially in models for observational synthesis (e.g., reanalyses) and observational syntheses for model validation and initialization (e.g., Obs4MIPs). At nearly the same time, the Lighthouse Activities were formed to create new centers of activity under the JSC with foci designed to address specific contemporary problems and applications.

ESMO was formed to coordinate WCRP units with modelling and observational missions, e.g., WGCM, WGSIP, WGNE from joint WCRP and WMO oversight. A motivation for ESOM involved the need for initiating, refining the mission of, or sunsetting other groupings as the SSG sees fit. This role provides flexibility enabling better collaborations with other Core Projects and Lighthouse Activities.

It is important to note that the other Core Projects and Lighthouse Activities retain strong modelling and observational capacity within their domains, e.g., the CLIVAR Ocean Model Development Panel (OMDP), the joint ESOM-Digital Earths LHA's km-scale Task Team, the Explaining and Predicting Earth System Change (EPESC) Working Group I and the Safe Landing Climate LHA. The ESOM coordination and

cross-cutting activities are available to any WCRP project with aligned interests through the SSG and IPO.

The two previous advisory councils WMAC (assessed modelling capabilities) and the WDAC (focal point for observations and data) were disbanded in 2020. The JSC intention in doing so was that ESMO would take over the joint responsibilities that these councils previously held.

ESMO partners

Recognising the broad and ubiquitous nature of modelling and observational activities within WCRP, to be effective in coordination ESMO must form connections and partnerships with all WCRP Core Projects (WCPs) and Lighthouse Activities (LHAs). ESMO will, when invited, participate in discussions about observations and modelling organised by these partners. The overarching goal is to enhance and advance the total capability of WCRP and its partners. Furthermore, ESMO will aim to act as an Earth system modelling and observations focal point for collaborations with external partners and other interested parties in government, non-governmental organisations, academia, and industry.

Within WCRP, ESMO seeks to establish or build on strong collaborations and cross-cutting activities with the observational and modelling panels and working groups of the core projects and LHAs. Such collaborations strengthen and make efficient communication across WCRP constituencies and communities and remove fragmentation and duplications. Cross-cutting activities help to advance existing WCRP modelling, data assimilation and observational efforts and connect them within an integrative framework under ESMO. ESMO intends to provide clear bridges to support activities in other core projects (e.g., the Global Extremes Platform in RfS, cross-WCRP focus on water-energy-carbon cycles). WGCM and CMIP have a long and productive working relationship with CORDEX, which is a key element of the proven pathway to regional downscaling that the group has mastered. At the same time, downscaling innovation activities (e.g., coupled downscaling and machine learning downscaling) in WGNE and WGSIP are connected to CORDEX through ESMO. Another focus is sharing data, knowledge, and opportunities within WCRP with a particular attention to data equity, including for the developing world.

ESMO works with many groups within and outside of WCRP: key participants are invited to relevant activities, communications and ideas for coordinated actions are welcomed from them, and ESMO fosters the collaborations of all its WGs with internal and external partners. An illustrative example is the WG on Numerical Experimentation (WGNE) which reports to the WMO Research Board and will continue to play a critical role in ESMO alongside the other modelling WGs. WGNE's role is to support the development of seamless modelling capability across timescales from weather to climate, jointly with WWRP and GAW. Within WCRP, WGNE will sit under ESMO governance and cross-cutting activities will strengthen the collaboration with other WGs (WGCM, WGSIP, WGORC).

Although not a complete list, ESMO has identified some partners within the WMO that are not part of the WCRP. ESMO will work closely with the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) and the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) Steering Groups and panels to support their role of assessing the status of global climate and ocean observations and producing guidance for improvement. The World Weather Research Programme (WWRP), the Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) and the Joint WMO/IOC

Technical Commission for Oceanography and Marine Meteorology (JCOMM) also all have objectives overlapping and aligned with those of ESMO.

Other parties that ESMO maintains contact with have a variety of sponsors and missions, but all have overlaps with the ESMO mission or community. These include regional and global scientific societies (e.g., AGU, EGU, AOGS), government agencies with aligned missions (e.g., space agencies like NASA, Copernicus, and JAXA, and weather and climate service agencies such as ECMWF and NOAA, and research federations like the U.S. Global Change Research Program (USGCRP) and the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF)), and observational coordination bodies (e.g., USCLIVAR, JCOMM). ESMO will also connect to broader stakeholders including the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the Global Framework for Climate Services (GFCS) and implementing initiatives such as the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), and WMO operational entities. Other external nongovernmental organization (NGO) partners include Future Earth, the Global Carbon Project, ClimateMatch, the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS). Links to CEOS's Coordination Group for Meteorological Satellites (CGMS) and Working Group on Climate (WG Climate) will allow ESMO to provide input to the space agencies on all issues related to climate monitoring from space.

Industry contacts (e.g., NVIDIA, IBM, Vaisala, OpenAI, Planet.com, and Google) will be sought to advance understanding of emerging technologies and industrial products of potential use to the ESMO community. Industry connections may be initiated by outside contact to ESMO, but will always be targeted toward ESMO objectives and activities as appropriate and in consultation with the JSC. Conflicts of interest, or the appearance of them, will be closely monitored when working with industry or government partners.

ESMO Objectives in Detail

1 - Advancing predictions and projections of the Earth system

The first ESMO objective focuses on improved predictive skills of the evolution of the climate system on time scales from weeks to centuries. The provision of science-based climate predictions and projections requires a coordinated model hierarchy connecting models at various scales from process models at cm-scale to regional models, global km-scale models and Earth System Models (ESMs) featuring a carbon cycle among many other processes. Such model hierarchy should be aligned in an integrative framework making use of Earth system observations and data assimilation practices to evaluate model prediction and projection skill and address an ever-expanding suite of applications.

Advancing predictions and projections of the Earth system needs to be based on accessible, reliable and useful modelling systems that simulate the Earth's climate system with demonstrable fidelity and process representation. An important aspect of this objective is to better understand different types of model uncertainty and accuracy and how they vary across scales. Another aspect focuses on reducing systematic model errors and biases, many of which have persisted across multiple model generations and are relatively well known (cf. WGNE systematic error workshops and survey). Improved model fidelity and enhanced predictive skills demand scientific and technical advances in the development and use of 1) Integrated experiment and evaluation frameworks, 2) New modelling approaches and 3) High resolution

modelling. Scientific aspects of these three topics are discussed below, while technical challenges are highlighted under Objective 3.

Topics

Integrated experiment and evaluation frameworks

Experiment and evaluation frameworks should be jointly developed, shared across the community and allow for the use of a model hierarchy. Existing analysis suites, evaluation tools and metrics (e.g., CMIP6 analysis, CLIVAR metrics and ESMValtool) have been extremely useful in the past. A future challenge is to extend these tools to work across wider modelling infrastructures beyond coupled models, to make them more accessible and interoperable and to include metrics that are better at capturing spatial patterns and regional details. Progress can be made by organising the development of a set of model and observational analysis suites that work in a diverse model landscape with the data and analysis being co-locate.

Observations play an important role for assessing model fidelity in standard and accessible ways, as has been the focus of various existing efforts (e.g., obs4MIPs). The consistency of observations is a prerequisite for their successful use in modelling evaluations and forcings. This applies to the evaluation of historical simulations, process evaluation, forcing datasets for climate models and the use of observational data sets for data assimilation from medium-range weather to decadal forecasts. As a first step, observational requirements for the analysis of the Earth system in the context of modelling need to be provided in a consistent, documented, and comprehensive manner. Furthermore, quantifying uncertainties in observational changes and error sources (see Objective 2 for further details) will give a better context to both improve and evaluate models. In addition to the improved use of observations, better use of reanalysis and paleoclimate information will benefit evaluation efforts.

Integrated experiment frameworks will require coordinated experiment design and model initializations as well as common standards and infrastructure. The various components of ESMs need different levels of initialization depending on their governing spatio-temporal scales. In particular for the ocean, land surface, soil, and ice sheets, special initialization procedures are necessary as the slow processes in these compartments lead to a much more pronounced dependency on the initial state. One possible approach to create realistic initial conditions for a component is to perform a spin-up run with the external forcing provided by an existing reanalysis. Another possible approach would be to apply a data assimilation cycle to the spin-up to accelerate the convergence of the component's model state towards a realistic representation. It is also important to address the unique challenges of biogeochemical (BGC) modeling and its coupling with physical processes. Including BGC considerations in initialization procedures and experiment designs will help advance our understanding of the interactions between biogeochemical cycles and climate dynamics.

New modelling approaches

A clear outcome of the 'Future of Climate Modeling Workshop' in 2022 was that no single approach should dominate the climate modelling efforts, but that instead different individual and combined modelling approaches are needed (Forster et al., 2023). These should include the further development of existing and new approaches such as process-specific models, digital Earths, improved Earth System Models,

physical emulators, and machine learning methods. Coordinated interaction with funders and stakeholders to support a multiverse of models through a codesign process will be important.

New modelling approaches can contribute to improved predictive skills of the evolution of the climate system. Model improvements through parameter estimation approaches and machine learning tools (see Objective 3 for details on the latter) need to be advanced while taking into account model resolution and usage of flow of information. Parameter estimation should make use of dynamical understanding and can occur across spatial regions and different dimensions. Another approach is the estimation of unknown mathematical formulations, e.g., through data-driven equation discovery.

To give one example, a fruitful new approach for improving model fidelity in the near term, is to apply in the model equations tendency bias corrections derived from data assimilation increments to represent “missing” tendencies, e.g., due to imperfect model physics or finite resolution. This technique has been shown to reduce systematic errors in several models and can improve the skill of initialised predictions. Machine learning approaches to mimic these increments as a function of model state even in the absence of new observations have also shown promise in bias correcting models. Further development and broader uptake of this approach could greatly benefit climate model applications and could contribute to identifying the sources of errors.

High resolution modelling

Representation of the water cycle and specifically improving the representation of organised tropical meso-scale convective systems and heavy precipitation is a fundamental challenge for weather and climate models. This entails a range of scientific issues such as interactions between the convective systems and large-scale circulation or cloud-aerosol interactions. Accurate modelling of these interconnected processes has been shown to require ultra-high resolution global and regional models (km-scale) which will need to be developed and integrated within a traceable hierarchy of weather and climate models.

The 2022 WCRP km-scale modelling workshop has highlighted the potential and challenges of ultra high resolution Earth System Models (WCRP, 2022). Recommendations from the workshop include the investigation of current scientific challenges in each model component as well as in the coupled models including the representation of deep convection, extratropical phenomena, boundary-layer clouds, and hydrology in collaboration with GEWEX’s GASS and GLASS, CLIVAR’s OMDP, CLiC, the Large Eddy Simulation community, GHP, and RHPs.

Global coupled simulations at km-scale show some promising improvements but also some large biases, often similar to those reported at coarser resolution. Dedicated Process Intercomparison Projects (PIPs) can be helpful for identifying and improving the representation of key processes in km-scale models that have been linked to such errors. Scale-aware parameterizations, efficient numerics and data formats, technological and computational advances, and other aspects of model formulations for the km-scale and beyond are of continual interest. Such projects should involve models and observations from global to km-scale and connect km-scale modelling communities with those studying processes in the various spheres.

Methods and Activities

Many of these challenges are already being addressed in the modelling WGs and observational panels that sit under ESMO and in other core projects and LHAs. These range from process understanding and development of component models (e.g., GASS within GEWEX; OMDP within CLIVAR) to assessment, intercomparison and evaluation of ESMs (e.g., CMIP, CCMI within SPARC). Here we highlight specific priority topics that ESMO is well-placed to address and that would yield rapid results and benefits to the modelling community and the broad user community that relies on model results. These include activities focused on model improvements via the reduction of systematic errors (a-d), the use of reanalysis and data assimilation (e-f), the coordination of observational activities in the context of modelling (g-i), as well as links to external partners (j).

ESMO's approach will be to promote and integrate work within ESMO WGs, other core projects and LHAs via targeted and focussed workshops, community papers and shorter-lived task teams (see section on Implementation and Methods of ESMO for further details). Workshops should be held regularly to exchange cutting-edge ideas and to jump start collaborative community efforts toward meeting specific objectives. Such workshops will be particularly effective if they include groups that normally have little interaction (e.g., weather and climate modellers, AI/ML experts) as well as Early Career Researchers (ECRs). Task teams will be addressing well defined topics or science questions and have limited lifetimes.

- a. ESMO-wide surveys of model development teams on their top concerns for model errors and shortcomings to prioritise problems on which to focus. This continues a longstanding WGNE activity and will be expanded on with the coordination of km-scale modelling efforts.
- b. Activities aimed at increasing the visibility, uptake, and understanding of the benefits of the tendency bias correction method (e.g., via dedicated intercomparison projects).
- c. Well-designed, international model intercomparison projects (e.g., to target specific model errors related to applied parametrizations and to test the performance of and need for certain model components).
- d. Coordination of work on interpreting, contrasting, and optimising the value of multi-model, single expensive ensemble member, and large initial condition ensembles, including opportunities for deeper interpretation of ensembles using statistical and machine learning approaches.
- e. Coordinate model initialization activities.
- f. Conduct multi-reanalysis combinations to provide improved variable and uncertainty estimates for the use of model verification and calibration.
- g. Develop near-term prediction systems including the carbon cycle in support of verification and monitoring activities.
- h. ESMO co-ordinated global survey of observational needs to support model evaluation that go beyond ECVs.
- i. Unifying simulated observation techniques for model-data comparisons, e.g., enabling comparisons to data at radiance level.

- j. Linking Research-to-Operations, through better integration of current and future activities across WCRP and WWRP communities.

Outcomes

Top level outcomes of the activities under this objective are to 1) identify, attribute, and reduce model systematic errors and to 2) enhanced skill of subseasonal to decadal predictions and long-term climate projections. In detail, the envisioned outcomes include:

- Recommendations on the use of model configurations for different applications.
- A traceable hierarchy of weather and climate models, including AI/ML models.
- Early warning capacity for weather and climate extremes and associated risk.
- Improved prediction skill and reduced model biases through application of tendency bias corrections derived from assimilation increments.
- Quantify impacts of model deficiencies on analyses and forecasts.
- Improvements in representation of small scale processes, e.g., tropical convection and its organisation.
- Best practices and a common understanding of observational uncertainties among the observation and modelling communities.
- Quantification of observational needs for modelling derived in a consistent way across all parts of WCRP at a global level.

These link strongly with objectives and WGs under the LHAs Explaining and Predicting Earth System Change and Digital Earths.

2 - Improving monitoring, understanding and attribution of climate system changes and impacts

Bringing together information from observations and models in coupled systems is critical for capturing and attributing the past evolution of the Earth system. Such knowledge will allow for a better understanding not only of the characteristics, but also of the impacts of climate change. Key aspects of this objective are enhanced process understanding and robust signal detection supported by consistent uncertainty quantifications in observational and reanalysis data sets. These goals demand advances in the areas of 1) Use and development of climate observing networks, 2) Benchmark reanalysis, 3) Uncertainty quantification as outlined below.

Topics

Climate observing networks

The climate observing system in the form of space-based and conventional observations is essential for physical process understanding, monitoring climate change and quantifying model fidelity. While a relatively rich spectrum of Earth system observations exists today with unprecedented spatial coverage, such an observing system needs to be maintained and further extended. Climate observations require dedicated cross-calibration and stability across different streams as well as optimised coverage in space and time. Identifying gaps in priority in-situ reference observations

needed for the validation of space-based observations and models is crucial, especially in sparsely observed areas such as the global south or deep ocean. Extended in-situ reference networks also play a big role for monitoring of extreme events.

Similar to in-situ observations, potential gaps in the satellite record need to be anticipated, as observations from space can provide a spatially and temporally complete record of critical climate variables. Furthermore, the combination and integration of in-situ and satellite-based observing systems can play an important role in developing our understanding of the climate system. For example, the sparse but direct measurements of the in-situ rain gauge network can be supplemented by spatially complete convective cloud information from satellites to support the early warning systems for tropical drought. Identification of complementarities and pathways for co-development represent an important component of an integrated observing system.

Observing System Simulation Experiments (OSSEs) can inform the design of observing systems by determining accuracy, cost-efficiency, and viability of existing and proposed observations within various model designs. Such information is important for variational approaches including sensitivity studies, passive monitoring activities, as well as nudging techniques for observationally constrained evolutions of simulations and reanalyses. These experiments also contribute to process understanding studies as well as detection and attribution of long-term climate changes. Interactions between the various bodies of WCRP and the observing community (e.g., GCOS, GOOS) is an important way to give feedback on the quality of existing data and areas where observations are missing.

Data assimilation and benchmark reanalysis

Data assimilation is often employed to generate monitoring data sets such as reanalyses in order to provide optimal retrospective time series as a synergy of model and observational information. With respect to Earth system approaches, the existing data assimilation methods have to be developed further, i.e., extended, and adapted. A special focus has to be given to the consistent representation of the different spatial and temporal scales that govern the processes in the various compartments of the Earth system. Therefore, adapted data assimilation approaches must be able to identify appropriate spatio-temporal structures near the interfaces of compartments in order to control information transfer across interfaces while at the same time retaining physical consistency in each compartment. Specific focuses should also be given to the construction of tangent-linear and adjoint models and the inclusion of currently missing processes, e.g., ocean and land biogeochemistry.

Reanalyses have to be temporally consistent over long periods of time to be able to draw meaningful conclusions on changes of the mean state or its variability. This requirement is, however, in conflict with the ever-changing observing system landscape which introduces jumps or artificial drifts in the reanalysis. Intensified homogenization efforts for observational time series and their utilisation in the next generation of reanalyses are required. Furthermore, the role of observational uncertainty for data assimilation products needs to be better understood. Another important step is the inclusion of more observations for parameters such as clouds, aerosols, soil moisture, land use and land surface coverage, bottom topography, ice shelves, loading and others in cooperation with the observing community. ESMO plays

an important role in collecting these lessons and cataloging the analyses that are available.

Uncertainty quantification

Quantifying uncertainties in observational changes and error sources will give a better context to improve and evaluate models. In addition, knowing the uncertainty in climate trends and variability is arguably as important as to understand the trends themselves, in order to avoid incorrect inferences or optimistic levels of confidence in conclusions drawn from observations. The combined use of observations, e.g., in determining energy budgets, requires consistent methodology to determine uncertainty estimates for the contributing variables. The dominant contributor to total observational uncertainty can vary substantially with spatiotemporal scale of interest. Therefore, the determination of uncertainty estimates for observations should consider all effects on measurements that cause error as well as error correlation characteristics and their propagation.

Uncertainty characterisation associated with the reanalysis's outputs will be a key element of future reanalyses. Some reanalyses made an important advance towards this goal by providing an uncertainty estimate based on an ensemble of realisations or a multi-model reanalyses ensemble. Systematic components of reanalysis uncertainties remain unknown and are a significant contribution to the uncertainties in quantities averaged over long-time scales or over large spatial scales. Estimating and validating this component of the uncertainty, in the production of a 'benchmark' reanalysis, will require in particular satellite observations with very well characterised, and small, uncertainties. Further, a strong collaboration of reanalysis producing centres is needed in order to foster exchange of data and knowledge and to define common standards for the evaluation and inter-comparison of reanalyses.

Methods and Activities

- Efforts on homogenization of observational data sets used as time varying boundary forcings for reanalyses and models ensuring best consistency with the observations and temporal consistency. They should be extended as far back as possible and include uncertainty estimates that could readily be propagated by the model into other variables.
- Promote the continuous curation of observation-space data sets of in-situ observations as input to data assimilation in reanalyses applications including data rescue, quality control, integration into collections, and inclusion of most recent observations.
- Implementation of a joint community effort on coordination of observing systems experiments (OSEs) and observing systems simulation experiments (OSSEs) for climate. These activities will be jointly developed with The Explaining and Predicting Earth System Change (EPESC) LHA and the Global Extremes Platform.
- Develop a common understanding of observational and reanalysis uncertainties via promotion of common vocabularies, concepts, and standards for documenting known error effects.

- Catalogue of available observational and reanalysis datasets used by the WCRP community including information on where they can be found.
- Establish a framework for enhanced exchanges among reanalysis producers with respect to the provision of observations as well as to implement common standards for evaluating and inter-comparing reanalyses with an application-oriented focus, especially considering changes in observational requirements for newer technologies such as ML based models.
- Develop methodologies and tools for handling observational uncertainties and coordinate common needs across modelling communities.
- Organisation of observation inter-comparison projects to identify and correct systematic errors, e.g., uncertainty quantification activity in ocean data sets.
- Implementing metrology concepts to quantify uncertainty in observational data sets at different time and space scales.
- Coordinate the solicitation and collection of observational requirements for carbon cycle monitoring across all of WCRP to be provided to GCOS for consolidation in the overall observing system requirements and advocacy.
- Develop recommendations for reconciling observational quantities with model requirements to clarify relation between closely related but distinct variables, through the use of synthetic observations or transfer function.
- Establish a strong interface to the space agencies through the CEOS/CGMS Working Group on Climate to provide guidance on the needs of the WCRP research community for space-based observation (e.g., of the carbon cycle and atmospheric composition).
- Promote the need for a coherent fully coupled land-ocean-atmosphere Carbon Cycle reanalysis of the recent past since 1990.

New and revitalised efforts on observations and reanalysis under ESMO will be required to deliver many of these activities. Joining up of ESMO work with GCOS and WWRP will be vital to success.

Outcomes

These strongly link with objectives and WGs under the LHAs Explaining and Predicting Earth System Change and Digital Earth as well as WWRP-DAOS.

- Improved monitoring and forecasting capabilities of the Earth system with enhanced methods for robust signal detection and uncertainty quantification
- Advanced data assimilation methodology for climate.
- Advanced data selection and curation processes.
- Written guidance on how to derive meaningful observational requirements in support of GCOS and expert groups advising agencies in ground-based network design or the definition of a space mission.
- Education of the upcoming generations of climate scientists to data assimilation.
- Provision of improved climate information for adaptation, serving societal needs.
- Facilitated exploitation of interface observations, and co-design of observing systems.

- Improved quantification of budgets in the energy, fresh water and carbon cycles.
- Observations and products become increasingly fit-for-purpose for ESMO science.

3 - Advancing and harnessing emerging technologies

New and emerging technologies impact all methods of operation in climate science including aspects of Earth system modelling and computation, new approaches in data assimilation and interpretation, as well as innovative observations. For instance, machine learning techniques can be exploited across the whole climate science and services chain, from observational quality control and model development to data assimilation, post-processing and end-to-end emulation of climate services. Improvements in technological efficiency and resource needs can also help reduce the carbon footprint of climate research itself, and allow for stronger collaborations with scientists from the Global South. Objective 3 aims at supporting and advancing the applications of such new technologies by the WCRP community.

Topics

Emerging technologies for data mining and post-processing

Advanced modelling efforts seeking to represent the global Earth system in ever finer detail are targeting cloud-resolving, km-scale resolutions. Such simulations require advanced computing and software architectures and generate immense amounts of data that must be stored, analysed, and served to the scientific and climate impacts communities. Emerging technologies such as machine learning will likely become indispensable for mining and interpreting this data. The challenges of distilling scientific understanding from model outputs will only magnify, so that hierarchies of weather and climate models, including simple reduced dynamics models, will continue to serve as vital points of reference.

There is clear potential to apply machine learning methods to post processing of model output for bias correction to enable use of predictions for services and societal applications across timescales from sub-seasonal to decadal. Neural networks have become a focus in this regard, allowing for complex non-linear dependencies to be exploited. While the results of the post-processing are likely enhanced through these approaches, the synthesis of multiple observational networks, spatio-temporal generalisations and downscaling efforts can also be implemented. There are challenges in preparing datasets for these purposes, however, which must be well-understood and studied in order to avoid inadvertently cementing biases (e.g., undersampling in the Global South) into the datasets or exacerbating misleading or systematic biases in the synthesis products.

Machine learning for emulators and parameterizations

With the rapid development of advanced technologies, new modelling approaches are emerging such as the integration of machine learning into model formulations. Recent results show that machine learning-based models are capable of competing with or outperforming existing dynamical models to forecast large-scale spatial patterns of weather and precipitation. They are also able to better calibrate and merge multi-model ensemble prediction output. A major challenge is to include such new approaches not only within individual components, i.e., as a process parameterization

or replacement for one, but also as emulators spanning across the various scales and components of the climate system. This may include substantial changes in how predictions and projections are delivered, and how model resolution, complexity or ensemble spread is measured. Other modelling challenges focus on technical issues such as exascale computing and coding, input/output and memory issues, debugging, and data formats.

Technological advances in the observing system

With respect to observations, new technologies and data products become more and more important driven by requirements for precise, high resolution and consistent observations of a growing number of climate science relevant variables. New types of observing platforms are expected to be increasingly used, e.g., surface or subsurface gliders and bottom-based observing platforms in the field of ocean science. Satellite technology is also changing rapidly with the development and advancement of small, low-cost satellites. Through their technological innovation, such small satellites enable entirely new architectures for a wide range of applications in climate science. Their greater flexibility and affordability will allow for testing new innovative components and products and provide greater interoperability with ground-based sensors.

Data formatting, conversion, and sharing

Standardisation of accessing, archiving, and processing climate data is crucial for the use of scientific data by a wide range of scientists globally. A common vocabulary between producers and users of data with agreements on standards and format, searchability and discoverability of the data is needed. There are considerable challenges for the global south and data sparse areas of the tropics to access high quality data highlighting the importance of fair and open access to data. Another important aspect is traceability of data processing throughout the data chain using consistent and standardised recording methods within the metadata, agreed upon between the modelling and observation communities. Cloud computing, particularly with associated analysis platforms, offers the potential for a much wider range of scientists globally to access and analyse observational and model data, but require additional financing that has not been budgeted for in traditional data repository design.

Design considerations for datasets involve many factors, so it is important for ESMO and its projects and panels to consult with each other and retain a broad view. Formatting for web sharing (rapid downloads or access to only limited parts of a large dataset), formatting that automatically includes metadata (e.g., NetCDF), and good practices in data transparency (keeping track of creators, versions, updates, and documentation) are important for both model and observational data.

Data curation for emerging technologies

Data-driven science has very particular needs, which are challenged by the historical reconstruction of past conditions and by the present accumulation of new data. Filtering and gridding that might be useful for data assimilation or model-observation comparisons may degrade the dataset's utility for machine learning. Biases within the data that may not be apparent in data assimilation purposes (where the assimilation method may correct or the dynamical model may ignore) can become pronounced in data-driven products. Digitization of historical data is part of the process in creating climate data, but data-driven science needs to account for the changing nature and

scale of collection of the data over time; this may require more metadata than past efforts have deemed necessary. Open access to datasets does not necessarily imply that they are ready for data-driven science, so resources for curating data for this purpose needs to be accounted for in data-driven projects and in preparing repositories for these purposes.

Artificial intelligence for chatbots and citizen science

Climate science observations can also benefit from citizen science contributions, which most often take the form of image interpretation or collection of in situ data. Both approaches can be highly useful for the calibration and validation of remotely sensed images. Engaging non-professional volunteers in scientific studies will enable the collection and interpretation of climate relevant information on a larger scale. Current challenges focus on data quality issues and on the question of how to engage citizen participation in the longer term. Large Language Models can be used to answer a wide range of questions based on the scientific literature, but phrased in multiple languages and appropriate for answering questions from citizen scientists. Truly integrated climate monitoring systems with data contributions from and embedded feedback for citizens have the potential to strengthen the role of citizen science in climate research.

Methods and Activities

ESMO will support activities for technical infrastructure including data access systems such as obs4MIPs and ESGF, cloud-based model evaluation tools, observation simulators, standard observation-based diagnostics tools, and requirements of new observational data for near-real time systems. ESMO will harness emerging technologies in collaboration with the LHA Digital Earth and related initiatives such as European Destination Earth in order to substantially raise the technological capabilities to model, monitor and simulate natural phenomena and related human activities. These activities will develop a range of computer and data access services specific to Earth system observations and modelling including the provision of hosted data processing in cloud infrastructure. Key activities will focus on ways of strengthening sustainability of technical systems for working with observations and model outputs and harnessing emerging technologies for climate modelling and research bringing best practice from research and operations closer together.

- Application of machine learning to develop physically constrained, scale-aware, and ideally stochastic parameterizations for subgrid-scale motions and fluxes informed by observational and modelling “big data”.
- Application of machine learning for post-processing of initialised climate prediction for services and societal applications across timescales from sub-seasonal to decadal, including forecast product creation, verification, and calibration.
- Application of exascale computing and data management. Help facilitate dialogues connecting climate modellers, software engineers, and hardware designers to proactively enhance mutual understanding of the climate community’s evolving needs and the developing tools needed to realize them.
- Promote and inform science applications involving new sensors and citizen science.
- Coordination of unification of data to common data types for rapid comparison.

- Promote interoperable forecast model databases that allow verification and calibration of model output across all time scales.
- Share best practices and knowledge on data policy, protocols, and standards via coordinated web-based tools.
- Provide a communication platform for tools for bringing models and observations together.
- Establishes partnership engagement with technical panels in WCRP, Destination Earth and other related activities inside and outside of WCRP and WMO inclusive operational entities.
- Maintain an understanding of the energy and carbon footprint of new technologies while making decisions and recommendations for emerging and renewal of systems.

Outcomes

Top level outcomes of the activities under Objective 3 are 1) Stronger engagement of the weather and climate modelling communities with emerging technologies, 2) Promotion of innovation in observations such as robotic platforms and new sensors, 3) Advancing model-data fusion through interoperability frameworks and smart databases and 4) Support and broadened application for sustainability of data and modelling infrastructure. These link strongly with objectives under the Digital Earths LHA.

- Human capacity building and promotion of co-design of projects between climate and computer scientists.
- Strengthening sustainability of technical systems for working with observations and model outputs (e.g., data access systems such as obs4MIPs, ESGF; new observational data for near-real time systems; cloud-based model evaluation tools; observation simulators, standard observation-based diagnostics).
- Promotion and wider use of the file/data standardisation and archive/dissemination infrastructure developed for CMIP across WCRP.
- Verification metrics and bias-correction strategies enhanced and tailored to stakeholder needs.
- Multi-model databases including cloud computing and big-data python-based software frameworks.

Pairing Objectives to Working Groups and Partners

All working groups will contribute to all three ESMO objectives with some WGs being the main contributors to a particular objective. In Table 1 the major internal contributors and the main internal and external partners are listed for each of the three ESMO objectives.

Objective	Main internal contributors	Main internal partners	Main external partners
Advancing predictions and projections of the Earth system	WGCM, CMIP, WGNE, WGSIP, DCP, Obs4MIPs	GSOP, OMDP, GLASS, GASS, CCMI, SNAP, EPESC, Digital Earths	WWRP, GCOS, GOOS, GAW, WG Climate, Future Earth

Improve monitoring, understanding and attribution of climate system changes and impacts	Obs4MIPs, WGORC	S-RIP, TUNER, GDAP, EPESC, Digital Earth	Global Carbon Project, WG Climate, CEOS, GCOS
Advancing and harnessing emerging technologies in modelling and observations	WGNE, WGCM, CMIP, WIP, WGSIP	Digital Earths	EU Destination Earth, Industry partners (Schmidt, Microsoft, NVIDIA, Google)

Table 1: Main internal contributors as well as the main internal and external partners for the ESMO objectives.

Cross-Cutting Science Themes

ESMO will identify a number of cross-cutting science themes that will strongly benefit from the coordinated model-observation framework and will be the focus of dedicated ESMO activities. We here identify five initial cross-cutting themes that are central to the WCRP scientific objectives. ESMO will continue to develop further cross-cutting themes as the project and working groups evolve.

Carbon Cycle

Understanding the fate of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions in the climate system is essential to quantify current and future climate change. Long-term monitoring of relevant processes (e.g., ecosystems and interfaces) is needed to detect their changes under anthropogenic perturbation. Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) currently lack a comprehensive overview of carbon cycle variables, omitting key process variables (e.g., lateral flows) and use cases (e.g., point source monitoring versus synoptic country-scale monitoring). Recent emphasis on cycles in GCOS offers ESMO an opportunity to establish an active interface with GCOS, particularly regarding carbon observation requirements.

Current Earth system models can improve their representation of physical and biogeochemical processes driving climate-carbon feedbacks. This is particularly relevant for terrestrial and marine ecosystems, as CMIP6 ESMs miss key processes such as soil carbon dynamics in permafrost, wildfires, and carbon cycle response to ocean warming, deoxygenation, and acidification. Biogeochemical processes in models are often not scale-aware, limiting compatibility with various resolutions and types of dynamical models. Long-term monitoring to support the evaluation of new parameterizations in ESMs is critical to reducing uncertainties in future projections.

Climate projections with ESMs typically use prescribed socio-economic emission scenarios. An alternative adaptive scenario approach aligns with the Paris Agreement's global stocktake process, where emission targets are regularly revised. Adaptive scenarios assess warming simulated by ESMs at intervals and adjust emissions for subsequent simulations to ensure a desired warming level by the end of the period. This approach allows direct quantification of the remaining carbon budget and its uncertainty, complementing ESMO's role in projection science.

Extremes

The second cross-cutting theme will focus on meteorological, oceanic, and hydrological extreme events at a global scale and their improved monitoring and predicting. This second cross-cutting theme will be closely developed with the Global Extremes Platform that sits under RfS. These intermittent phenomena challenge data acquisition (modeling, observations) and data storage (they are not well-represented in time-averaged fields), and so techniques for collection, storage, and definitions of extreme events are areas where ESMO science can assist.

Parameterizations and Emulators

A third cross-cutting theme is the development of parameterizations for processes within climate models and emulators of entire climate model components or indeed of the whole climate system. These simplified representations combine theory, a diverse set of modelling approaches, process observation, and increasingly, machine learning. Many observational campaigns and high-resolution process models are targeted at collecting information to improve parameterizations, but there are few meetings about developing them. On the other hand, Emulators are increasingly being used to widen the span of future scenarios and speed understanding of policy implications. If they are to remain useful, they must be of high scientific quality, transparent in their assumptions, and routinely evaluated against full Earth system models.

Data Assimilation and Statistical Modelling

Unlike weather modelling and forecasting, climate models have only recently been used in forecast systems. This is partly due to the chaotic nature of weather which makes climate model projections distinct from weather model predictions, but also due to the technical challenges that arise from trying to use observations to simultaneously constrain the fast components of the Earth system (e.g., atmosphere) with the slow components (e.g., ocean). Through WGNE and WGCM, ESMO has the breadth to work across all of these modelling scenarios from weather timescales out to centuries ahead.

Coupled data assimilation techniques seek to address the challenge of utilising constraints from observations collected in different parts of the earth system. The increasing use of the ensemble Kalman filter with large ensembles of climate model projections reveals that there is both an interest and a need for the seasonal to decadal forecasts enabled by these technologies. Reanalysis and state estimates are also helpful tools in understanding the context for observations and linking different classes of observations together to arrive at a fuller understanding of the processes indicated by the observational constraints.

Finally, statistical and probabilistic approaches to climate modelling and projection are tools that are increasingly used in studies of the climate and weather. Bayesian emulators and large ensembles are two examples of approaches used in modelling probabilistic futures, but there is much to be learned in considering the probabilistic nature of models together with uncertainty quantification.

Managing Slow and Fast Earth System Components

As mentioned above, coupled data assimilation is challenged by phenomena with disparate timescales in the Earth system. Similarly, experimental design is also challenged, as it may take centuries or millennia for the deep ocean and ice sheets to

completely spin up, a cost that is unwieldy in high-resolution modelling. A better understanding of the useful constraints from paleoclimate reconstructions on climate models is a major part of efforts within ESMO such as PMIP, but opportunities for numerical advances and coordinating data transfer from paleoclimate archives into datasets useful for evaluating paleoclimate models can use the support of ESMO's wider scope.

On the much shorter timescales of the observational record, our instruments deployed for decades or centuries require calibration and analysis to arrive at climate-quality data capable of capturing the slow changes in the system. The challenges of sustained observations—from a human, technical, and financial perspective—need the support of groups such as ESMO that value these long data records that constrain slow change in their many applications.

Implementation and Methods of ESMO

ESMO Structure

The ESMO management and governance establishes the operating framework and stands alongside the ESMO science and implementation plan to oversee activities. It lays out the structure of the management (Figure 2), and covers the core groupings, their membership, and the lines of reporting. The full Terms of Reference for each of the different groups mentioned here are available in the ESMO Zenodo community page.

ESMO Scientific Steering Group

The ESMO Scientific Steering Group (SSG) has the overall responsibility for planning and guiding the work of the Core Project. The SSG will oversee all scientific activities and directions of the individual ESMO working groups, projects, panels and task teams in order to achieve the above discussed science objectives. In this context the SSG will identify and initiate new activities as well as collaborations with WCRP internal and external partners. The SSG will work closely together with the IPO.

SSG members represent modelling, data assimilation and observations across all climate-related disciplines in atmospheric, oceanic, hydrological and cryospheric sciences. By taking on roles as points of contact with all ESMO groups and WCRP activities, the SSG members will ensure close collaborations among these bodies and provide guidance and advice when needed. Membership on the SSG follows the WCRP guidelines for core projects (currently a tenure for 4 years, with two possible extensions of 2 years each).

International Project Offices

ESMO International Project Office (ESMO IPO)

The ESMO IPO is responsible for the overall ESMO management and coordination. It supports and provides advice to the SSG and implements SSG decisions.

The ESMO IPO works in close cooperation with the ESMO co-chairs, SSG members, the WCRP leadership, and the WCRP Secretariat. It serves as the major

communication channel and the primary point of contact for those wishing to participate in, contribute to, or learn more about ESMO activities.

The ESMO IPO maintains regular contact with all WCRP Core Projects and Lighthouse Activities. The ESMO IPO especially maintains connections with subgroups that aim to advance science with alignment or overlap with the ESMO Objectives.

CMIP International Project Office (CMIP IPO)

The CMIP International Project Office coordinates the CMIP project under the CMIP Panel for the experimental design and associated requirements and the WCRP Infrastructure Panel (WIP) for infrastructure matters.

Working Groups

ESMO WGs oversee, facilitate and support the international community in all activities and projects that carry out the ESMO scientific programme. The WGs are long-standing organisational elements of ESMO. Co-chairs and memberships of the WGs are appointed by the ESMO SSG.

Working Group on Coupled Modelling (WGCM)

- WGCM coordinates the development and review of coupled climate models aimed at understanding natural climate variability and predicting the response of the climate system to changes in natural and anthropogenic forcing.

Working Group on Subseasonal to Interdecadal Prediction (WGSIP)

- WGSIP aims to develop a programme of numerical experimentation for subseasonal-to-interdecadal variability and predictability, with an emphasis on assessing and improving predictions.
- WGSIP oversees the Decadal Climate Prediction Project (DCPP) which coordinates the scientific and practical aspects of decadal climate prediction research within WCRP.

Working Group on Numerical Experimentation (WGNE)

- WGNE has responsibility for the development of Earth system models for use in weather, climate, water and environmental prediction on all time scales, and diagnosing and resolving shortcomings. WGNE is jointly supervised by WCRP and the WMO research Board.

Working Group on Observations for Researching Climate (WGORC)

- WGORC focuses on improving communication and collaboration between the climate modelling and observation research communities to facilitate an easier and more beneficial use of observations in climate modelling. The group will serve as a platform to address challenges, identify opportunities, and ensure observations are optimally leveraged to enhance earth system model predictability and utility.

- WGORC oversees the obs4MIPs panel.

Projects and Panels

ESMO projects and panels are organisational elements related to the working groups that target specific scientific goals and outcomes. Their lifetime may be long or indefinite, and they consult with their Working Group and the SSG to assess continuing community needs.

Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP)

- The objective of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) is to better understand past, present and future climate changes arising from natural, unforced variability or in response to changes in radiative forcing in a multi-model context. This understanding includes assessments of model performance during the historical period and quantifications of the causes of the spread in future projections. Experiments are also used to increase understanding of the model responses and to investigate the predictability of the climate system on various time and space scales.
- An important goal of CMIP is to make the multi-model output publicly available in a standardized format.
- CMIP is supported by the CMIP International Project Office (CMIP-IPO).

WCRP Infrastructure Panel (WIP)

- The WIP is charged with coordinating infrastructure support for CMIP. It works with projects funded to develop software and supporting infrastructure that facilitates access to and analysis of the CMIP model output. It defines specifications and standards that ensure model output in a common structure and format that is archived and made accessible worldwide in a common way.
- WIP provides guidance and oversees infrastructure development so that it will be fit for its purpose and meet the scientific needs of CMIP and other MIP projects.
- WIP is supported by the CMIP International Project Office (CMIP-IPO).

Observations for Model Intercomparisons Projects (Obs4MIPs)

- Obs4MIPs aims at making observational data more accessible for climate model evaluation, development and research by providing observational products technically aligned with climate model data.
- Obs4MIPs facilitates ESM evaluation via technical alignment of gridded observational products with CMIP protocols. The technical alignment is accomplished by open source metadata/data integration of the two projects, facilitating side-by-side delivery of both via the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF)
- Obs4MIPs is supported by the CMIP International Project Office (CMIP-IPO).

Decadal Climate Prediction Project (DCPP)

- DCPP investigates the ability to skilfully predict climate variations from a year to a decade ahead by means of a series of retrospective forecasts.

Task teams

ESMO task teams are shorter-term organisational elements of ESMO that target specific scientific goals and outcomes. Their lifetime is connected to envisioned deliverables that are set when the task teams are formed. Their terms of reference are approved by the SSG. Co-chairs, and memberships of the task teams are appointed by their parent body at time of formation.

Km-scale Modeling ESMO-Digital Earths Task Team

- This group is coordinating activities around km-scale modeling within WCRP, especially meetings. They discuss and advance the development of km-scale coupled global and regional Earth System Models by sharing information on the construction and use of such models. The group will provide regular updates on the most pressing shortcomings and challenges as well as recommendations for future developments with respect to km-scale coupled models.

ESMO Modes of Work

Meetings

The ESMO SSG meets in person biennially, preferably in a joint-meeting format aligned with other ESMO WGs or PnPs annual meetings. These biennial meetings will also serve as a place to engage with the broader WCRP communities, seeking synergies with other CPs and LHAs and triggering debate and progress on identifying, reviewing and pushing forward scientific community goals. ESMO seeks to identify gaps, redundancies and inefficiencies, and to introduce members across groups. The ESMO IPO, with guidance from the SSG, will build competency and capabilities to facilitate international meetings in-person and online between groups within and outside of WCRP. Through practiced meeting formats, ESMO will help to identify gaps and bridge communities, and how to best utilize the resources of the ESMO IPO toward the WCRP and scientific community goals.

Community Papers

Another mode of work for ESMO is coordinating community papers. These may be white papers, newsletter articles or bulletins (e.g., [A Paradigm Shift for Climate Modelling for Climate Services](#)), or peer-reviewed state-of-the-science review papers drawing together authors from the ESMO groups, projects, and teams along with other WCRP and external scientists.

Schools and Capacity Building

Becoming an effective scientist in international modelling and observation activities involves many highly specialized skills and knowledge. In order to ensure continuing excellence in science for the many societal and environmental challenges to come in a changing and diverse world, ESMO will partner with the [WCRP Academy](#) and other interested external partners such as the [ClimateMatch Academy](#) to help bring the latest tools and ideas for modelling and observational science to young people and interested scientists worldwide. The ESMO IPO will build a scientist directory of all members and co-chairs, past and present, of its WGs, PnPs, and TTs as a resource for those seeking specific expertise for educational programs. The ESMO IPO will also gather resources, such as the community papers and outcome reports of meetings that it helps coordinate, in the plan that they may be valuable in education and capacity building.

Strengthening ESMO's engagement with Global South

To enhance knowledge sharing and foster greater collaboration with researchers from the Global South, our project will adopt a multifaceted strategy that seeks to enhance both representation and active participation, addressing the historical underrepresentation of perspectives and scientists from these regions in Earth system research. This includes increasing the representation of Global South scientists on ESMO panels to integrate diverse perspectives and regional expertise. Additionally, we will organize strategically located meetings and summer schools, addressing both logistical and academic needs for participants from underrepresented regions. To further support this engagement, ESMO also aims to provide travel support, helping scientists to attend key meetings and contribute to advancing Earth system research globally.

Web Presence and Open Access

Within the IPO staff, expertise in building web pages will be used to gather information to improve data management, data access, best practices, and present practices. As part of ESMO's Objective 3 (Advancing and harnessing emerging technologies), sharing information about emerging technologies such as cloud computing, machine learning, and artificial intelligence tools with the modelling and observation communities is central. All ESMO documents, such as meeting reports, white papers, and peer-reviewed papers will be open access.

List of Abbreviations

APARC - Atmospheric Processes And their Role in Climate
CLIVAR - Climate and Ocean Variability, Predictability, and Change
CMIP - Climate Model Intercomparison Project
CEOS - Committee on Earth Observation Satellites
CGMS - Coordination Group for Meteorological Satellites
CPs - Core Projects
ESGF - Earth System Grid Federation
ESMO - Earth System Modelling and Observations
IOC - Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
IPO - International Project Office
JSC - Joint Scientific Committee
LHAs - Lighthouse Activities
MIP - Model Intercomparison Project
NGO - non-governmental organization
obs4MIPs - Observations for Model Intercomparisons Projects
OMDP - Ocean Model Development Panel
PnPs - Projects and Panels
RIfS - Regional Information for Society
SSG - Scientific Steering Group
SPARC - Stratospheric Processes And their Role in Climate
TTs - Task Teams
UNESCO - United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
GCOS - Global Climate Observing System
WIP - WCRP Infrastructure Panel
JCOMM - WMO/IOC Joint Technical Commission for Oceanography and Marine Meteorology
WGs - Working Groups
WGCM - Working Group on Coupled Modelling
WGNE - Working Group on Numerical Experimentation
WGORC - Working Group on Observations for Researching Climate
WGSIP - Working Group on Subseasonal to Interdecadal Prediction
WCRP - World Climate Research Programme
WMO - World Meteorological Organisation
WWRP - World Weather Research Programme
WWRP-DAOS - WWRP Data Assimilation & Observing Systems

Links to Relevant Glossaries

<https://apps.ipcc.ch/glossary/>

https://19january2017snapshot.epa.gov/climatechange/glossary-climate-change-terms_.html

https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/media/document/CCKP_glossary.pdf

<https://climatepromise.undp.org/news-and-stories/climate-dictionary-everyday-guide-climate-change>

https://unfccc.int/resource/cd_roms/na1/ghg_inventories/english/8_glossary/Glossary_.htm

References

A WCRP vision for accessible, useful and reliable climate modelling systems: Report of the Future of Climate Modeling Workshop, online. Ed. Piers Forster, Vaishali Naik, Detlef Stammer, Helen Cleugh, Nico Caltabiano, WCRP Publication 03/2023.

World Climate Research Programme, 2022. Report of the WCRP km-scale modeling workshop, 8/2022, 3-7 October 2022, hybrid format.